

A STUDY ON SOFT SKILLS MANAGEMENT FOR PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Cite This Article: R. Indira & Dr. K. Vellaichamy, "A Study on Attitude towards Teaching Profession for Self Financed School Teachers", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 372-374, 2018.

Abstract:

Teachers are the most critical component of any system of education. How well they teach depends on motivation, qualification, experience, training, aptitude and a mass of other factors, not the least of these being the environment and management structures with in which they perform their role. This is the ability of a person to develop a deep understanding of something. It helps a person to understand the environment in which he/she lives and problems which might prevent him or her from making proper decisions. Before making a decision, a critical thinker considers the advantages and disadvantages of various ways of doing something. Critical thinker helps a person to come up with ideas to solve problems.

Key Words: Soft Skills Management and Prospective Teachers

Need for the Study:

Thinking is one of the major aspects of cognitive behavior. Thinking provides the base to person on which cognitive, affective and cognitive domains of behavior depends which properly justify the comment like- "think before you act". Thinking has a definite purpose and end. It always initiates with some difficulty and ends in its solution. The solution of the problem includes the exploration of the problem mental manipulation of the objects, activities and experiences. Thinking styles are not like the intelligence; intelligence refers to the individual capabilities, potential and abilities to perform the task however, thinking styles refers to the individual preferences (Seif, 2008). Style is neither cognition not personality but the combination of them. Thinking style is the ways an individual prefers to conceive information. It also refers to the individual's priority to think about information or task both during and after learning process. Sternberg explains that individuals have not only a one specific style but a set of profile of styles which helps people to adjust with their abilities according to environmental needs and demands. So the present study intends to measure to soft skills management which is entitled the present study, "Soft Skills Management for Prospective Teachers".

Terms and Definitions:

- Soft Skills Management - refers to the quality character and interpersonal skills of a person's contacts.
- Prospective Teachers: refers to students studying B.Ed. programme in Madurai District.

Variables of the Study:

Dependent Variable:

- Soft skills management

Independent Variables:

- Gender
- Nativity
- College Kind

Objectives of the Study:

- To compute the stage of soft skills management among the prospective teachers.
- To discover the significant influence of independent variables

Hypotheses of the Study:

- Soft skills management among the prospective teachers is above the average level.
- Gender exerts a significant influence on Soft skills management among the prospective teachers.
- Nativity exerts a significant influence on Soft skills management among the prospective teachers.
- College kind exerts a significant influence on Soft skills management among the prospective teachers.

Sample of the Study:

- A random sample of 360 prospective teachers in Madurai District

Tools Used:

- General Information Sheet developed by the Investigator.
- Soft skills management scale developed by Kumar, A (2014).

Statistical Treatments:

- Mean
- Standard Deviation
- 't' test

Studies Related to Soft Skills:

Swati Mujumdar (2011) Need for Vocationalisation of Education in India. The purpose of this study is to assess and describe the importance and need for Vocational education at higher and primary levels and soft coping skills and general educational skills also bring out the present Indian and International Education scenario and its problems. The study also recommends for policies for implementation at State and National Level and suggests possible models to introduce soft coping skills and general educational skills and Vocational Education at the higher/ tertiary levels in India. This concept will emphasize on a different teaching – learning pedagogy with a special focus and attention on skill based learning and training and emphasizing soft coping skills and general educational skills such as competencies, entrepreneur skills, problem solving, team work, leadership, management courses etc. Teachers training will be given special emphasis in order to build teaching resources and research component.

Aparna.N and Raakhee (2011). Soft Skill Education for Adolescents: Its Relevance and Importance. Imparting soft skill education through curriculum will help adolescents to overcome complexities and difficulties of soft and can play a remedial role in solving problems to lead a better soft. So the study focuses on soft skill education essential for the society and every education system should integrate and impart soft skill education as a part of its curriculum to develop positive health behavior, positive interpersonal relationships and well being of individuals.

Bindhu David, Shiny John (2011). Soft Skills and Attitude towards Vocation among the Vocational Higher Secondary and Higher Secondary School Students. The study is an attempt to find the Soft Skills and Attitude towards Vocation and their relationship. The study shows a relation between Soft Skills and Attitude towards Vocation among the Vocational Higher Secondary and Higher Secondary School Students of standard XI and will help educators to frame an effective curriculum. The present study is a descriptive survey. The investigator has used self-made Soft Skills Scale and Vocational Scale. The sample for the present study includes 500 boys and girls of Vocational Higher Secondary and 250 boys and girls of Higher Secondary School Students. Statistical methods like mean, standard deviation and t-test were used. From the analysis of the objectives, we conclude that Soft Skills and Attitude towards Vocation among the Vocational Higher Secondary and Higher Secondary School Student shows a positively weaker correlation. So as the soft skills increase, a favorable attitude towards vocation develops the soft skills score will also increase.

Hypothesis Verifications:

Hypothesis 1: The average score of the Soft skills management among prospective teachers is 38, theoretical average is 30. Hence the hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: Soft skills management Gender

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	‘ t’- value	Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	102	38.59	8.72	0.531	Not Significant
	Female	258	38.07	7.66		

It is evident from table 1, that the obtained ‘t’ value 0.531 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between the male and female prospective teachers in terms of Soft skills management among prospective teachers. Further, it is observed that gender does not influence on Soft skills management among prospective teachers. Hence the hypothesis 2 is rejected.

Hypothesis 3:

Table 2: Soft skills management Nativity

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	‘ t’- value	Significance at 0.05 level
Nativity	Rural	197	38.37	8.19	0.506	Not Significant
	Urban	163	37.94	7.71		

It is evident from table 2, that the obtained ‘t’ value 0.506 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between the rural and urban prospective teachers in terms of Soft skills management among prospective teachers. Further, it is observed that Nativity does not influence on Soft skills management among prospective teachers. Hence the hypothesis 3 is rejected.

Wise:

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	‘ t’- value	Significance at 0.05 level
College kind	Unisex	166	40.28	8.26	2.240	Significant
	Co-education	194	38.06	7.13		

It is evident from table 3, that the obtained ‘t’ value 2.240 is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between the unisex and co-education colleges’ prospective teachers in terms of Soft skills management among prospective teachers. Further, it is observed that unisex college prospective teachers have more on Soft skills management than co-education. Hence the hypothesis 4 is accepted.

Conclusions:

The major conclusions arrived at from the study are listed below:

- Soft skills among the prospective teachers are found high.
- Soft skills among the prospective teachers are found dependent on College kind.
- Soft skills among the prospective teachers is found independent on Gender and Nativity

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